

The Influence of Transformational Leadership on Employee Performance in The Salapian District Office, Langkat District

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Abstract

The purpose of this research is to determine and analyze the influence of transformational leadership on employee performance at the Salapian District Head Office. This research was conducted using a causal associative quantitative approach. The sample used was all company employees, with a total of 50 people. The research results show that transformational leadership has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. This is shown by the T-count value of 3.193 which is greater than the T-table of 1.67722, as well as the P-Value value of 0.002 which is smaller than 0.05. The regression coefficient shows that if transformational leadership is increased by 1 unit, employee performance will increase by 1,319 units assuming other variables remain constant. Apart from that, the results of the determination test show an Adjusted R Square value of 0.150 or 15.00%, which indicates that transformational leadership has a low influence on employee performance, while the remaining 75.00% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied. Thus, partially, transformational leadership has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at the Salapian Subdistrict Office, Langkat Regency. This identifies that, meaning, improvements in transformational leadership can contribute to improving employee performance.

Keywords: Transformational Leadership; Employee Performance

INTRODUCTION

The success or failure of an organization in maintaining its existence starts from managing human resources by empowering and maximizing the potential of existing employees to be more productive at work (Amalia, 2022). In an effort to realize the goals of an organization, whether in the business or public sector, good and maximum employee performance has a very important role and main duties.

According to Amaliah & Sakir, (2023) one of the crucial aspects that needs to be considered is the level of transformational leadership in the organization. Transformational leadership, which includes the leader's ability to inspire, motivate and guide employees to ensure the achievement of common goals. The explanation above is still not actually able to be realized by every organization where the current real conditions show that almost all companies or organizations are faced with complex challenges in managing employee performance.

In this context, it is important to understand how transformational leadership can shape and influence employees' levels of affective commitment. This statement is supported by the results of research conducted by Ambalele & Tellu (2023) which states that transformational leadership has a significant impact in the context of HR management, increasing employee job satisfaction and organizational commitment.

Leaders who apply a transformational leadership style will be able to build a strong sense of attachment and commitment from employees (Iqbal, 2021). This statement is the

basis for understanding the internal dynamics of an organization that can influence overall employee performance.

Based on the results of the author's initial observations through observations and interviews with the Salapian Subdistrict Head, the real conditions that occur in the Subdistrict Office are the emergence of dynamics and challenges regarding changes in the work environment, increasingly complex task demands, as well as structural changes in the organization which can provide an important context for understanding how Transformational leadership can be applied and have an impact on employee performance. Thus, it is hoped that this research can make a significant contribution in optimizing employee performance at the Salapian Subdistrict Office, as well as providing an in-depth understanding of the role of transformational leadership and affective commitment in the organizational context.

This research has very important relevance in the context of human resource management in government offices, especially the Salapian District Head Office. By looking at the conditions faced by many organizations today, including the dynamics and challenges experienced by the Salapian Subdistrict Office, this research will provide a deeper understanding of how transformational leadership can play a role in improving employee performance.

This is relevant because good and maximum employee performance is very important for the success of an organization, especially in facing the complexity of tasks and changes in the work environment (Fadilah & Wilian, 2023).

In order to realize the goals of an organization, both in the business and public sectors, good and maximum employee performance has a very important role and main duties. In realizing these goals, organizations or agencies are often faced with various obstacles and challenges that can impact poor and optimal performance results. The success or failure of an organization in maintaining its existence starts from managing human resources by empowering and maximizing the potential of existing employees to be more productive at work (Amalia, 2022).

The current real condition is that almost all companies or organizations are faced with complex challenges in managing employee performance. One crucial aspect that needs to be considered is the level of transformational leadership within the organization (Amaliah & Sakir, 2023). Transformational leadership, which includes the leader's ability to inspire, motivate and guide employees, is an important factor in ensuring the achievement of common goals.

According to (Fahmi, 2017) Performance is the result of a process that is referred to and measured over a certain period of time based on previously established provisions or agreements. Meanwhile, according to (Afandi, 2018) employee performance is the result of work that can be achieved by a person or group of people in a company in accordance with their respective authority and responsibilities in an effort to achieve organizational goals illegally, does not violate the law and does not conflict with morals and ethics. .

To measure performance in this research, it refers to the indicators stated by (Afandi, 2018), namely as follows:

1. Quantity of work output;
2. Quality of work results;
3. Efficiency in carrying out tasks;
4. Work discipline;
5. Initiative ;
6. Accuracy;
7. Leadership;
8. Honesty; And
9. Creativity.

To achieve maximum performance, many factors can influence it. This research is limited to leadership factorstransformational. In research, transformational leadership is defined as a leadership approach that causes change in individuals and social systems. In its ideal form, it creates valuable and positive changes in followers with the ultimate goal of developing followers into leaders (Djuraidi & Laily, 2020).

To measure the implementation of transformational leadership, this research refers to indicators formulated by (Robbins, Stephen P. & Mary Coulter, 2010)

1. Charisma is considered to be a combination of personal charm and magnetism that contributes to an extraordinary ability to get others to support a vision and also promote it enthusiastically.
2. Inspirational Motivation which describes a leader who is passionate about communicating the idealistic future of the organization.
3. Intellectual Stimulation which describes leaders as being able to encourage employees to solve old problems in new ways.
4. Individual Attention: Attention that illustrates that the leader always pays attention to his employees, treats employees individually, trains and advises.

The purpose of this research is to explore the relationship between transformational leadership and employee performance, at the Salapian District Head Office. Through a deeper understanding of the relationship between these variables, this research aims to provide concrete and relevant recommendations for the management of the Salapian Subdistrict Office in improving employee performance and strengthening their commitment to the organization. Thus, the aim of this research is not only to produce new knowledge in the field of human resource management, but also to make a significant contribution in increasing the effectiveness and productivity of the Salapian District Head Office in carrying out its duties and responsibilities. The concept of this research is as depicted in the conceptual framework imagethe following :

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

METHOD

This type of research is casual associative quantitative research with the aim of analyzing the pattern of relationships between variables with the aim of finding out the influence between two independent variables (exogenous) on the dependent variable (endogenous) (Kuncooro, Munajad, 2013). This research was carried out at the Salapian District Head Office. This research was carried out from March to May 2024. According to (Sugiyono, 2018) population is a generalized area consisting of objects/subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics determined by the researcher to be studied and then conclusions drawn. The population in this study is the entire number of employees in the Salapian District office with a total of 50 employees with the following details:

Table 1. Total Population

No.	Level of education	Number of people)
1.	Strata-2 (S2)	4
2.	Strata-1 (S1)	13
3.	Diploma-III (D3)	5
4.	high school	26
5.	junior high school	3
Total		50

Source: Salapian District Office, Langkat Regency

The sampling technique used in this research was a saturated sample. According to (Sugiyono, 2019) Saturated sampling is a sample selection technique if all members of the population are sampled, where the entire population in this study is sampled, namely 50 employees.

The data that will be used from this research is the data from the questionnaire distributed to respondents consisting of all employees in all divisions. The data analysis technique used in this research is a quantitative data analysis method using SPSS version 25.0.

Validity and reliability tests were carried out in order to test the quality of the research data. The validity test decision making criteria are as follows: If $r_{count} > r_{table}$, then the question item is valid. If $r_{count} < r_{table}$, then the question item is invalid. Meanwhile, the reliability test criteria are formulated if $r_{alpha} > r_{table}$ then the statement is reliable and if $r_{alpha} < r_{table}$ then the statement is not reliable.

The linear regression model was formulated in this research with the following formula: $Y = a + bX$

Where :

Y = Employee Performance

X = Transformational Leadership

a = Constant

b = Regression coefficient

The t-test in this research was carried out to determine the significance of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable (Kuncooro, Munajad,

2013). According to (Kuncooro, Munajad, 2013) the determination test (R^2) is used to measure how much influence the independent variable has on the dependent variable. In other words, the coefficient of determination is used to assess the magnitude of the influence of the independent variable studied, namely transformational leadership (X), on the dependent variable, namely employee performance (Y). The coefficient of determination (R^2) value ranges from zero to one ($0 < R^2 < 1$) which means, if $R^2 = 0$, then there is no influence between variable (X) and variable (Y). Conversely, if R^2 approaches 1, then the influence between variable (X) and variable (Y) becomes stronger. Testing of the coefficient of determination was carried out using SPSS version 25.0 software.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Contents Results and Discussion

1. Research result

a) Descriptive Analysis

Descriptive Analysis This test is used to determine the minimum and maximum scores, the highest score, the rating score and the standard deviation of each variable. The results are as follows:

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics

Variable	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Transformational leadership	50	1.75	5.00	3.6150	.73923
Employees' Performance	50	1.67	5.00	3.5710	.73840
Valid N (listwise)	50				

The table above shows that the measurement results show that respondents assess transformational leadership and employee performance at the Salapian District Head Office, Langkat Regency as above average, with mean values of 3.6150 and 3.5710 respectively on a scale of 1-5. The variation in respondents' assessments of these two variables is quite moderate, with almost the same standard deviation (0.73923 for transformational leadership and 0.73840 for employee performance), indicating that although there are individual differences in perceptions, the majority of respondents have quite positive views of these two variables.

b) Validity and Reliability Test Results

Validity Test Results

The validity test is used to measure whether a questionnaire is valid or not. Validity testing carried out in this research was through the Corrected Item-Total Correlation test or better known as Person Correlation.

Table 3. Validity Test Results for Transformational Leadership Variables (X)

Variable	Correlation Value	Probability	Information
X1	0.866 > 0.2787	0.000 < 0.050	Valid

X2	0.804 > 0.2787	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
X3	0.804 > 0.2787	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
X4	0.880 > 0.2787	0.000 < 0.050	Valid

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25

From the data above it can be stated that the indicators for the gender variable have a correlation coefficient value of > 0.2787 with a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$ so it can be concluded that the indicators for the transformational leadership variable are valid (Sugiyono, 2017).

Table 4. Validity Test Results for Employee Performance Variables (Y)

Variable	Correlation Value	Probability	Information
Y.1	0.690 > 0.2787	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
Y.2	0.898 > 0.2787	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
Y.3	0.885 > 0.2787	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
Y.4	0.701 > 0.2787	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
Y.5	0.892 > 0.2787	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
Y.6	0.892 > 0.2787	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
Y.7	0.914 > 0.2787	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
Y.8	0.885 > 0.2787	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
Y.9	0.858 > 0.2787	0.000 < 0.050	Valid

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25

From the data above it can be stated that all indicators on the employee performance variable have a correlation coefficient value greater than 0.2787 with a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$ so it can be concluded that the statements for the employee performance variable are valid (Sugiyono, 2016).

Reliability Test Results

According to (Ghozali, 2016) the reliability test aims to measure how reliable or reliable the questionnaire distributed to respondents is, which is useful as an instrument in this research. The reliability measurement method used in this research is by looking at the Cronbach Alpha (α) value. The questionnaire is declared reliable if the Cronbach Alpha (α) value is > 0.61 .

Table 5. Reliability Test Results

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
Transformational leadership	0.862	4
Employee Performance	0.950	9

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25.0

Based on table 5, it is known that the Cronbach Alpha (α) value of the transformational leadership and employee performance variables is greater than 0.60. So it can be concluded that all indicators in the variable instrument are declared reliable or reliable so that they can proceed to research hypothesis testing

c) Quantitative Analysis

This analysis is intended to determine the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable. The test results are as follows:

Simple Linear Regression Analysis

This regression test is intended to determine changes in the dependent variable if the independent variable experiences changes. The test results are as follows:

Table 6. Simple Linear Regression Test Results

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	8,708	5,933		1,468	,148
	Transformational leadership	1,319	,413	.408	3,193	,002

Dependent Variable: Student Learning Motivation

Based on the test results in table 8, the regression equation $Y = 8.708 + 1.319X$ is obtained. This equation is explained as follows: 1) A constant of 8.708 means that if there is no transformational leadership, then there is an employee performance of 8.708 points. The regression coefficient for transformational leadership is 1.319, meaning that transformational leadership influences an increase in employee performance of 1.319 for every 1 point increase.

Analysis of the Coefficient of Determination

To determine the magnitude of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable, a coefficient of determination analysis was carried out. The test results are as follows:

Table 7. Coefficient of Determination Test Results

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.408a	,167	,150	11.39696	,167	10,197	1		,002

The test results in table 7 show an Adjusted R Square value of 0.150 or 15.00%, which means that transformational leadership has a low influence on employee performance, while the remaining 75.0% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied.

t Test Results (Hypothesis Test)

Hypothesis testing with the t test is used to determine whether or not there is an influence of the dependent variable on the independent variable with the following hypothesis formulation:

Ho: There is no influence of transformational leadership on employee performance at the Salapian Subdistrict Office, Langkat Regency

Ha: There is an influence of transformational leadership on employee performance at the Salapian Subdistrict Office, Langkat Regency

The following are the results of the hypothesis test as shown in the following table:

Table 8. Hypothesis Test Results

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	8,708	5,933		1,468	,148
Transformational leadership	1,319	,413	,408	3,193	,002

Dependent Variable: employee performance

Based on the test results in table 8, the calculated t value is $3.193 > t$ table 1.67722 , with a significance value of $0.002 < 0.05$, thus it can be stated that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted or that there is a positive and significant influence between transformational leadership on employee performance at the Salapian District Head Office Langkat Regency.

Contents of Discussion Results

The findings in this research can be strengthened by referring to relevant previous research findings. In the context of the influence of transformational leadership on employee performance, these findings are in line with research results (Deddy, 2022) and (Fadilah & Wilian, 2023a) which show that there is an influence between transformational leadership and employee performance.

The implication of these findings is that in implementing transformational leadership, it is important for leaders to pay more attention to how this concept is applied practically in concrete work environments. This includes ensuring that the organization's vision and values are internalized effectively by all team members, facilitating open and two-way communication between leaders and employees, and paying attention to individual needs and preferences in team management (Muktamar & Pinto, 2023).

CLOSING

Conclusion

From the results of the research data analysis and discussion described above, it can be concluded that:

1. The results of the hypothesis test show that transformational leadership has a positive effect on employee performance. This can be seen from the T-count value of $3.193 > T$ -table 1.67722 with a P-Value value of $0.002 < 0.05$. This regression coefficient shows that if transformational leadership is increased by 1 unit, the change in employee performance as seen from the Y value will increase by 1.319 units assuming other variables are considered constant. Thus, partially, transformational leadership has a positive and significant effect on employee job satisfaction at the Salapian District Head Office, Langkat Regency.

2. Based on the results of the termination test, it shows that the Adjusted R Square value is 0.150 or 15.00%, which means that transformational leadership has a low influence on employee performance, while the remaining 75.0% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied.

Suggestions

Based on the results of the discussion and conclusions of this research, several things can be suggested to institutions, including:

1. Strengthen the implementation of transformational leadership to improve employee performance. Leaders must be more active in internalizing the organization's vision and values to all team members. This step can be done through leadership training that focuses on developing the ability to inspire and motivate employees, as well as ensuring that the organization's core values are understood and applied in daily activities. In addition, leaders need to continue to communicate organizational goals clearly and consistently to maintain focus and clear direction for employees.
2. Institutions must also facilitate open and two-way communication between leaders and employees. This can be realized through regular meetings, feedback sessions, and formal and informal mechanisms that allow employees to convey ideas, complaints, or suggestions. By creating a work environment that supports open dialogue, institutions can build trust and stronger relationships between leaders and employees, which in turn will improve performance and job satisfaction.
3. Additionally, it is important for institutions to consider individual needs and preferences in team management. Transformational leadership must be adapted to the characteristics of each employee to maximize their potential. Institutions can conduct regular individual needs assessments and provide career development programs that suit employee aspirations. By paying attention to these individual aspects, institutions not only improve performance but also create a work environment that supports employee professional and personal growth, which ultimately will increase loyalty and productivity.

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